

Synthesis and Characterization of Zeolite-A

Ajeng Sekar Oktaviana Nugrahadianto¹, Michelle Axelia Setio², Dewi Aulia Fadhillah³

^{1,2,3}Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Technology, Airlangga University,

Email : michelle.axelia.setio-2021@fst.unair.ac.id

Abstract

Zeolite A is a material developed as a solution to the inconsistent crystallinity and impurities found in natural zeolites. It is a synthetic aluminosilicate that has numerous applications in catalysis, ion exchange, and molecular adsorption. This study aims to synthesize and characterize Zeolite A to explore its potential as an optimized synthetic zeolite. The synthesis process involved reacting sodium aluminate, sodium hydroxide, and tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), followed by hydrothermal treatment, drying, and calcination to ensure complete crystallization. Characterization was performed using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) to identify structural bonds and gravimetric analysis to determine solid acidity. The synthesized Zeolite A has a yield of 61.08%. FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of aluminosilicate framework vibrations and the total solid acidity measured through gravimetric analysis is 2.9062 mmol/g. These results validate the effectiveness of the synthesis process, providing insights into the structural and acidic properties critical for industrial applications.

Keywords: Zeolite A, Zeolite Synthesis, FTIR, Solid Acidity

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INTRODUCTION

Zeolite is a mineral in the form of hydrated aluminosilicate crystals composed of silica and aluminum tetrahedra with each oxygen limiting the two tetrahedra (Valdes, Perez Cordoves, and Diaz-Garcia, 2006). Zeolite is an important material for several reactions that occur as catalysts, ion exchangers, adsorbents, and molecular sieve applications. The unique properties of each zeolite allow its use in various sectors including the agricultural, industrial, and other sectors.

In Indonesia, zeolites are commonly found in an almost pure form and have relatively cheap prices. Most types of zeolite contain a positive charge of alkaline earth metal ions in a three-dimensional crystal framework. The structure consists of three primary components: the aluminosilicate skeleton, the interconnected empty space containing metal cations, and water molecules (Suwardi, 2009).

There are two types of zeolite: natural and synthesized. Natural zeolite is formed due to the complex chemical and physical processes of stones that undergo various changes in nature. Naturally formed zeolites have the general formula $M_{x/n}(Al_xSi_yO_{2(x+y)})_z \cdot H_2O$, where M is a metal cation with an n charge (Las & Zamroni, 2002). From the general formula above, it is stated that natural zeolite contains water. Water is a polar molecule that is easily adsorbed on the surface of zeolite, therefore natural zeolites always contain water. This is due to the small size of the zeolite molecules; water will fill all the channels and cavities in the zeolite crystal (Valdes, Perez Cordoves, and Diaz-Garcia, 2006).

However, some studies explained that the composition of natural zeolite depends on the state of temperature, location, and radiation. These various natural conditions lead to the existence of many types of zeolites. Despite this, various types of zeolites have similarities in their texture (Las & Zamroni, 2002). There are various kinds of minor components that make the crystallization often occur poorly. The minor components include Na, K, Ca, Mg, and Fe (Atikah, W.S., 2017).

Synthetic zeolite is a widely developed product to prevent poor crystallization. It is a type of zeolite made by engineering in such a way to get a better character than natural zeolite. Synthetic zeolites are divided into several groups according to the ratio of Al and Si components in the zeolite.

Synthetic zeolites, such as types A, P, X, and Y, primarily differ in their aluminum (alumina) content, which affects their crystal structure and ion exchange capacity. Higher alumina and sodium content in the zeolite enhances both the ion exchange capacity and the dissolution rate. Zeolite A features a sodalite cage structure that forms a cubic framework with four-sided rings. In contrast, type P zeolite, which belongs to the gismondin family has its own characteristics. Zeolites X and Y share the faujasite (FAU) structure. However, zeolite Y has a higher Si/Al ratio ($>1-1.5$), making it more spherical with a pore diameter of approximately 0.74 nm and a larger surface area (Dongoran, Sulistiawati, Simangunsong, Paksi, & Pasaribu, 2021). Both types of zeolite are important in modern-day industry, with the world demand for zeolite has continued to increase. Synthetic zeolite was estimated to be approximately 1.8 million metric tons while the demand for natural zeolite was projected to hit 5.5 metric tons by 2010 (Kulprathpanja, 2010).

With the high utilization of zeolite in various sectors, the identification of zeolite needs to be done before moving on to the next step. Therefore, this scientific paper is prepared with the aim of providing information related to the synthesis and characterization of zeolite.

METHOD

Tools and Materials

The tools used in this experiment were beaker glass, measuring cylinder glass, glass pipette, thermometer, hot plate stirrer, aluminum foil, glass stirring rod, polypropylene bottle, stand and clamp, porcelain crucible, analytical scales, desiccator, oven, agate mortar, infrared spectrophotometer, and OriginPro®2018 software.

The materials used in this experiment were sodium aluminate (NaAlO_2), tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), potassium bromide (KBr), ammonia (NH_3), and aquadest.

Synthesis of Zeolite A

Zeolite A was synthesized by dissolving 6.5576 grams of sodium aluminate (NaAlO_2) in 40 mL of distilled water (aquadest). Stir the mixture thoroughly using a magnetic stirrer until fully dissolved. In a separate beaker glass, dissolve 1.6772 grams of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) in 30 mL of distilled water. Once fully dissolved, pour the NaOH solution into the prepared NaAlO_2 solution. Stir it constantly to ensure a homogeneous mixture. Next, using a pipette, alternately add 27.2 mL of distilled water and 8 mL of tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) to the solution, adding each dropwise. Continue this process slowly, allowing each addition to mix well before adding the next. Once all components are combined, heat the mixture to 50°C and maintain this temperature for one hour. After heating, transfer the mixture to a polypropylene bottle and place it in an oven set at 100°C for two hours to promote crystal growth. Once completed, pour the solution into a beaker for further processing.

To neutralize the solution, wash it thoroughly with distilled water until the pH reaches a neutral level. Then, dry the precipitate formed in an oven at 100°C until fully dried. Finally, heat the dried precipitate in an oven set to 450°C for four hours to perform calcination. This step ensures complete crystallization and removal of any remaining organic components, resulting in purified zeolite A. Weigh the synthesized zeolite A.

Characterization of Zeolite A

To determine the types of bonds in the synthesized zeolite A, begin by finely grinding the zeolite A sample using an agate mortar. Mix the powdered zeolite with potassium bromide (KBr) 1:100 to enhance the quality of the infrared transmission. Next, place the mixture into an FTIR sample holder and position it within the FTIR (Fourier-transform infrared) spectrometer. Perform the FTIR analysis to obtain the spectral data. Analyze the resulting FTIR spectra to confirm the zeolite's characteristic bonds.

Gravimetry is used to determine the solid acidity of the synthesized zeolite. Begin by preheating a porcelain crucible in an oven set to 120°C for 10 minutes. After heating, transfer the hot crucible to a desiccator and allow it to cool for 5 minutes. Weigh the crucible using analytical scales. Repeat the heating, cooling, and weighing steps until the crucible's weight becomes constant, indicating it is fully dried. Next, weigh 0.1 grams of the synthesized zeolite and place it in the dried crucible. Set up a desiccator containing the zeolite sample and a separate porcelain crucible with

ammonia (NH₃). Leave the setup in the desiccator for 24 hours. After 24 hours, remove the zeolite sample from the desiccator and allow it to sit in open air for at least 30 minutes to stabilize. Finally, weigh the crucible containing the zeolite that has absorbed ammonia. Calculate the amount of absorbed ammonia to determine the solid acidity of the zeolite.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of Zeolite A

Zeolites are naturally occurring or synthetic microporous aluminosilicates (Dar, B.A., 2019). In this research, synthesized zeolite was obtained in the form of white powder as much as 3,3462 grams, indicating that this method was effective in extracting Al and Si using NaOH. Zeolite synthesis was also carried out with the addition of tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) as a source of silica. During the heating process, silicate and alumina dissolve in water, initiating the formation of zeolite crystals. After the heating process, a hydrothermal process is done to enhance crystal growth that has begun since the interaction between silicate and aluminate salts, resulting in a white precipitate. The precipitate is then dried to evaporate the water and solvent trapped in the pores of the zeolite crystals, so the pore area increases. Finally, the calcination process is performed to solidify and stabilize the zeolite framework, ensuring greater structural stability.

The yield can be counted by:

$$\text{Yield} = \frac{\text{synthesized zeolite mass}}{\text{theoretical mass}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Yield} = \frac{3,3462}{5,47815} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Yield} = 61,08\%$$

Picture 1. Synthesized Zeolite A

Types of Bonds in Zeolite A

Diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS) is used to determine the types of bonds in zeolite A. This method is particularly effective for analyzing powdered or crystalline substances in the mid-IR and near-IR regions of the spectrum. It can also be used for analysis of unknown solid samples. In DRIFTS, samples are grounded with IR transparent salt, such as potassium bromide (KBr). This technique will produce an accurate measurement with little preparation. Another advantage of using the DRIFTS technique is that it provides a rapid technique for analyzing samples without any interference through sample preparation (Frost and Johanson, 1998).

Potassium bromide (KBr) is used as a blank and a diluent. This salt serves this purpose because potassium bromide does not absorb infrared (IR) radiation in the wavenumber range that is being observed, so it prevents interference with the sample spectra. The synthesized zeolite A sample is finely ground with KBr salt to dilute it, as the absorption of IR radiation by pure solid samples is often very strong. This is usually done to reduce the concentration of the sample and obtain better spectra (Nasar & Salisu, 2014). The data collected from the FTIR analysis is then processed using the OriginPro®2018 software for further interpretation and detailed analysis.

This characterization aims to identify the functional groups that make up the zeolite framework. The resulting spectra are in the form of absorption bands, where the location of the absorption band in the IR spectra is expressed by the wave number (cm⁻¹), while the intensity of the

absorption band is expressed by the percent transmittance (%T). The spectra of the synthesized zeolite A can be seen in Picture 2 meanwhile the analysis can be seen in Table 1.

Picture 2. FTIR Spectra of Zeolite A

Table 1. FTIR Analysis

No.	Wave-number (cm ⁻¹)	Vibration	Structural Fragments
1.	3715	Stretching	-O-H
2.	1763	Bending	Si-OH or Al-OH
3.	1003	Stretching asymmetries	Si-O-Al or Si-O-Na
4.	679	Stretching symmetries	Si-O-Si or O-Si-O
5.	563		Double ring (D4R)
6.	474	Bending	Tetrahedral structure Si-O-Al

One characteristic of zeolite is the presence of a double ring (D4R), indicated by absorption in the 600 – 550 cm⁻¹ range. In the zeolite structure, there are internal and external linkages. This double ring represents the external link between one zeolite layer and another. The bending vibrations of Si—O and Al—O within the aluminosilicate framework of zeolite appear around the absorption region of 400 cm⁻¹. The presence of both stretching and bending vibrations of Si—O and Al—O indicates the formation of the aluminosilicate framework in the sample (Saraswati, 2015).

Determination of Solid Acidity

One of the characteristics of zeolite that affects its performance is its acidic properties. The acidic properties affect the catalytic ability of zeolite, which is commonly used as a catalyst in various reaction processes (W. Li, et al., 2016).

The gravimetric method is carried out by measuring the amount of gas absorbed on the surface of the catalyst so that the acidity of the catalyst can be known. The solid acidity of zeolite was calculated by measuring the number of millimoles of ammonia base from the gas phase adsorbed by the surface of the zeolite. Ammonia is used as the absorbate base, assuming that the small molecular

size of NH_3 allows it to enter the pores of the zeolite and interact with the catalytic active side scattered on the surface and pores of the zeolite.

The active side binds to the acidity of zeolite derived from the Brønsted acid and Lewis acid sites in the zeolite structure. Brønsted acid sites are the sites that are capable of donating protons (H^+) and are usually formed by hydrogen atoms bonded to oxygen atoms in a zeolite skeleton. Meanwhile, the Lewis acid site is a site that can accept free electron pairs because it has empty orbitals and is often formed by metal atoms in the zeolite structure. Brønsted acid can be converted to Lewis acid by heating at high temperatures. Meanwhile, Lewis acid can turn into Brønsted acid with H_2O in zeolite accompanied by heating (Tatsumi, 2004).

Picture 3. Brønsted acid and Lewis acid sites on zeolites (Tatsumi, 2004).

This treatment begins with several times heating the porcelain crucible in the oven and then putting the crucible into the desiccator until the mass of the crucible is constant to remove any contaminant and moisture content. Then, weigh the porcelain crucible filled with zeolite A and put it into a desiccator with a crucible of ammonia (NH_3). A desiccator is used as a vacuum system to prevent any other bases or H_2O that can be absorbed by the zeolites. Inside the desiccator, the volatile NH_3 will evaporate and react with zeolite A. The reaction will form a coordination covalent bond between NH_3 and Al from zeolite. After 24 hours of incubation, evaporation after the desiccator is carried out for a minimum of 30 minutes to remove the remaining NH_3 that does not bind to the zeolite. Then zeolite will be weighed to determine the mass of the adsorbed NH_3 .

Table 2. Data of Mass After Treatment

Treatment	Mass (gram)
Porcelain crucible after the first heating process	40,8897
Porcelain crucible after the second heating process (A)	40,8860
Porcelain crucible + zeolite before incubation in a desiccator (B)	40,9951
Porcelain crucible + zeolite after incubation in a desiccator (C)	41,0005
Mass of the zeolite (B-A)	0,1091
Mass of the absorbed NH_3 (C-B)	0,0054

The total acidity of zeolite can be calculated using the following equations:

$$SA = \frac{m\text{NH}_3 \times 1000}{MW \text{NH}_3 \times m \text{zeolite}}$$

$$SA = \frac{0,0054 \times 1000}{17,031 \times 0,1091}$$

$$SA = 2,9062 \text{ mmol/g}$$

NB:

- SA : solid acidity (mmol/g)
 m NH₃ : mass of absorbed NH₃ (g)
 M zeolite : mass of zeolite (g)
 MW NH₃ : molecular weight of NH₃ (g/mmol)

The results of the characterization can be seen in Table 2. Then, the data was calculated to obtain the total acidity value of zeolite A solids which is 2.9062 mmol/g. The acidity of the zeolite A solids is affected by two factors such as the surface area and the duration of exposure to the desiccator. A larger surface area leads to a higher total acidity, as it allows for more interaction with ammonia. Similarly, the longer the incubation period in the desiccator, the more ammonia (NH₃) is absorbed, which corresponds to a higher total acidity of the solid.

CONCLUSION

The synthesized zeolite A weighed 3,3462 grams with a 61,08% yield. Zeolite A's bonds can be identified by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). Solid acidity of zeolite A is measured by the gravimetric method, resulting in 2,9062 mmol/g.

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